

Determinants of Undernutrition among Rural Female Adolescents: Indian Scenario

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Nutrition plays a crucial role at every stage of life cycle. Nutritional needs changes as per requirement and age. If not provided in an adequate amount, it may lead to serious consequences like malnutrition, anaemia, calcium deficiency and other micronutrient deficiencies. It becomes more important in adolescence which is also considered a critical period especially for girls. Adolescence is characterized by physiological, psychological and emotional transition. A period which prepares a body to bear a child and reserve more nutrients in terms of fat, protein and micronutrients, failing to which may lead to adversities in future like infections, illnesses and low survival of child at birth, low birth weight babies etc. Therefore, proper nutrition in this age specifically for girls must be ascertained. Apart from it, peer pressure, family environment, society, economic conditions and availability of resources also influence eating behaviour and thus impact nutritional status of girls. The issue becomes more challenging for the girls from rural background. Illiteracy, poor economic status, low resources, hygienic conditions, sanitation facilities and a tradition of early marriages make this period more complex. The present review addresses the determinants of undernutrition among rural adolescent females aged 10-19 years providing insights that may play a crucial role in the eradication of undernutrition and improvement in nutritional status.

Keywords: Adolescent girls, hygiene, malnutrition, public health, sanitation, underweight

Nutrition plays a crucial role at every stage of life cycle. It nourishes each cell of the body which is important for well being of any individual. Nutritional needs changes as per requirement and age. If not provided in an adequate amount, it may lead to serious consequences like malnutrition, anaemia, calcium deficiency and other micronutrient deficiencies (WHO, 2018). It becomes more important in adolescence which is also considered a critical period especially for girls. Adolescence is derived from the Latin word 'Adolescere' which means "to grow" or "to (mature)". A critical phase which is a period of 10-19 years (Damon, 2004). This period has been divided into early (10-14 years) and late adolescent (15-19 years). This period is characterized by physiological, psychological and emotional transition (Jain, 2024). A period which prepares a body to bear a child and reserve more nutrients in terms of fat, protein and micronutrients, failing to which may lead to adversities in future like infections, illnesses and low survival of child at birth, low birth weight babies etc. Therefore, proper nutrition in this age specifically for girls must be ascertained. Apart from it, peer pressure, family environment, society, economic conditions and availability of resources also influence eating behaviour and thus impact the nutritional status of girls.

The issue becomes more challenging for the girls from a rural background. Illiteracy, poor economic status, low resources, hygienic conditions, sanitation facilities and a tradition of early marriages make this period more complex. Due to this, a poor survival rate of mother and infants may result. Globally, 21% of girls

from 15-19 years of age and about 30% girls from low and middle-income countries are married (Arthur, 2017; UNICEF, 2018). Instead of various interventions and adolescent targeted interventions programmes, adolescent health has been compromised. Poshan Abhiyan 2.0 (2022) focused on late adolescent girls in underdeveloped regions, the initiatives remain deficient (Das, 2024; MoWCD, 2022). Rural Adolescent girls are sensitive to an unhealthy living environment, unhygienic places and unawareness and illiteracy make these situations worse. All these circumstances increases the probability of infections, illness and thus directly impact on nutritional status. Primary care facilities and health centres play a major part in analysing and communicating undernutrition among adolescents. The present review addresses the determinants of undernutrition among rural adolescent females aged 10-19 years providing insights that may play a crucial role in the eradication of undernutrition and improvement in nutritional status.

Method

Various search engines like Science Direct, Research Gate, PubMed, Google Scholar and Science.gov were employed to select the research articles on undernutrition among rural adolescent girls. Research papers based on Indian studies were collected and reviewed. All studies followed NCHS/WHO growth standards (Tables 1 & 2) to define undernutrition.

Indicators

To evaluate the degree of malnutrition among adolescent girls (10-19 years), the NCHS/WHO growth standards (2007) guidelines have been used by the researchers. The data on weights, heights and BMI were classified according to Z scores mentioned below.

Cut off point as $> +2$ SD was considered "overweight", -2 SD to $+2$ SD was considered "normal", < -2 SD was considered "moderately malnourished and < -3 SD was considered "severely malnourished".

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Table 1*Z- Score Classification of Malnutrition (WHO, 2007)*

Cut-off point	Classification
+2 SD to -2 SD	Normal
-2 SD to -3 SD	Moderate
< -3 SD	Severe

Table 2*Indicators for Assessment of Malnutrition NCHS/WHO Growth Standards (2007)*

Indicator	Cut-off point
Stunting	height-for-age <-2 SD
Wasting	weight-for-height <-2 SD
Underweight	weight-for-age <-2 SD
Thinness	BMI-for-age<-2SD

Stunting- It represents growth reduction due to poor diets and long-term nutritional deprivation leading to risk of illness and recurrent infections. Females with low height may face the risk to deliver low birth weight babies, resulting in increased risk of malnutrition and stunting (WHO, 2025).

Wasting- Wasting represents acute undernutrition, usually as a consequence of low food intake. Wasting diminishes the activity of immune system and may aggravate the occurrence of infectious diseases (WHO, 2025).

Underweight- Low weight for age represents it. Long-term underweight can lead to severe undernutrition in body and may increase the occurrence of infection and illness.

Thinness- Body Mass Index (BMI) is calculated by dividing weight (Kg) by height (m²) and it is compared with respect to age of individual which represents the thinness or obesity.

Review of Literature

All the reviewed Indian studies have been tabulated in Table no. 3. A community based cross-sectional study was conducted in Peeranwadi village of District Belgaum, Karnataka among 400 adolescent girls of aged 10 to 19 years. 63.82 and 60.79% of 10-14 years of adolescent girls were found to be stunted and thin. For girls in late adolescence (15 to 19 years), these values were documented as 40.84% for stunting and 39.43% for thinness by researchers. The researchers believed that a major reason for malnutrition in the rural area is low dietary intake which had been recorded as less than 50% of RDA (1272.20 kcal/day) with 40.99 gm protein and 14.42 mg of iron intake (Baliga et al., 2014). Another cross-sectional study conducted among 10-19 years old adolescents in the rural area of Ramnagara District of Karnataka reported 26.6% adolescent girls underweight (Johnson et al., 2015). Likewise, another cross-sectional study was conducted to assess the eating habits and nutritional status of 150 school going adolescent girls (10-19 years) of rural area of West Bengal and found significant association between different age groups, consumption of roots and tubers, cereals, green non leafy vegetables, fatty foods, eating at fast food centre, skipping of meals and physical activity (Sarkar et al., 2015). The prevalence of thinness and stunting was reported as 16% and 20.7% respectively. The researchers focused on nutritional interventions and counselling on healthy eating habits in school to improve the nutritional status of adolescent girls. In other

community based cross-sectional study by Choudhary et al. (2015) 10-19 years of 273 rural adolescent girls were assessed to study energy balance and protein intake of adolescent girls in a rural area of Haryana. Two-thirds of the adolescent girls were found to be underweight. Another community based cross sectional study conducted by Nair et al. (2017) in 10 villages of one of the districts of Maharashtra on nutritional status of rural adolescent girls. A total of 583 girls of an average age of 13.95 years were interviewed. Among them underweight and stunting were found 36.54% and 48.37% respectively with a significant association between underweight and marital status. Age group, religion and educational status were also found to be significant with stunting. Another community-based cross-sectional study in 252 adolescent girls of rural Puducherry to assess nutrient intake was conducted. Most of the adolescent girls (average age 13.79 years) were recorded as non-vegetarians (91.3%). The results say that due to consumption of junk food (5.6%), prevalence of overweight (13.5%) was found more as compared to thinness (10.7%) among adolescent girls. Consumption of cereals (97.4%) and pulses (54%) was satisfactory but regular vegetable (34.5%) and fruit (13.1%), milk (10%) and iron-rich foods (<2%) were consumed low. Targeted nutrition-education intervention was suggested to promote fruit and vegetable intake (Chandar et al., 2018).

Discussion

Malnutrition is a global public health problem. India is facing this issue in every age group. Most vulnerable groups include children 5-59 months old, children, adolescent girls and pregnant women in urban and rural areas. One major determinant behind this is poor dietary pattern like poor food/nutrient intake, eating habits which is further associated with many factors stemming from psychosocial and individual factors like body image, health status, poor appetite, socio cultural norms like gender biasness, societal pressure, early marriages, environmental issues like poor hygiene, sanitation, socioeconomic factors like income, education level of self and parents, family structure, physiological factors like pubertal development, frequent infections and illness, limited healthcare facilities. These determinants are multifaceted and require integrated interventions targeting these interconnected drivers for effective prevention and cure of malnutrition among adolescent girls. Unavailability, inaccessibility and poor purchasing power of rural households result in lower intake of food as compared to requirement for long period of time often leading to malnutrition and micronutrient deficiencies (Chandar et al., 2018; Ravula et al., 2024). Beside it, frequently skipping meals (especially breakfast) and irregular eating patterns are directly linked to high underweight prevalence. This may be due to fasting for cultural or religious reasons or starving body to get perfect body image which impacts regular food and nutrient intake and promotes malnutrition (Nair et al., 2017; Zafar et al., 2025). An individual's self-perception of their health status, for instance to perceive that one's health is worse as compared to peers is an independent predictor of malnutrition risk and among adolescent girls, peer and social pressures regarding body image and weight can contribute to distorted eating habits (Johnson et al., 2015). Apart from it, poor appetite is often an important consequence of low self-perceived health, psychological stress or physiological changes among adolescent girls and a significant and independent determinant of malnutrition risk as it directly impacts food intake (Ans et al., 2018). The onset of puberty

Table 3*Various Indian Studies on Undernutrition among Rural Adolescent Girls (10-19 years) and Associated Factors*

S. No.	Study	Mean Age of Study Group (Years)	Study area	Sample size (No.)	Socio-economic Status	Literacy level	Marital Status	Undernutrition			Mean Calorie intake	Other Factors found associated
								Under weight (%age)	Stunting (% age)	Thinness (% age)		
1	Baliga et al. (2014)	12.9 ± 2.06	Peeranwadi village of Belgaum, Karnataka	400	Lower	High school	Unmarried	-	59.75	57	1272.20 ± 133.28	education of subjects and their mothers
2.	Johnson et al. (2015)	14	Rural area of Ramnagara District of Karnataka	79	-	-	-	26.6	-	-	-	-
3.	Sarkar et al. (2015)	13.33 ± 1.09	Rural area of West Bengal	150	Not defined	9th	-	-	20.7	16	-	Joint family, Menarche attained
4.	Choudhary et al. (2015)	Not defined	Rural area of Haryana	273	-	-	-	65.56	-	-	-	-
5.	Nair et al. (2017)	13.95 ± 2.48	Rural area of Maharashtra	583	Lower	High school	Unmarried	36.54	48.37	-	-	Nuclear family
6.	Chandar et al. (2018)	13.79 + 2.11	Rural Puducherry	252	Below Poverty Line	Higher Secondary	-	-	-	10.7	-	Parents' Education

dramatically increases the body's nutrient requirement and adjustment with psychosocial issues also make undernutrition a major concern for adolescent females (Das et al., 2024) because it leads to frequent infection and illness. Malnutrition is a vicious cycle. Undernourished adolescent girls often suffer from infection and illness due to poor immunity and insufficient food intake becomes them severely undernourished. As far as socio-cultural norms are interconnected with malnutrition among adolescent girls, early marriage and pregnancy are among the major concerns. Although in the studies included in the review, few married adolescent girls were documented (Baliga et al., 2014; Nair et al., 2017). Increased awareness, literacy and parents support in some places are changing the scenario; however, early marriage malpractice in India exists mostly in rural areas. Early pregnancy creates extra physiological pressure on developing bodies, which ultimately depletes the nutrient reserves of the body. Regular monthly flow, poor food intake and child responsibility, the new mothers who did not complete their school and have poor knowledge of nutrition are not able to take care of their health properly. Apart from it, gender-based discrimination in food distribution within the household prioritizing males, leaving girls with smaller or less nutritious portions increase the risk of malnutrition among females. Socioeconomic factors, viz., income, parental education and awareness, family structure collectively impact the health status of girls (Paul et al., 2023; Ravula et al., 2024). In all the listed studies, the subjects belonged to a lower

socioeconomic status. Low purchasing power is a primary driver of undernutrition among adolescent girls. Due to a poor source of income and a large family size, per person distribution of food sources does not fulfil the daily food/nutrient requirement of adolescents leading them to be underweight and thin. Most of the parents studied till High school. Therefore, it may be expected from them to have enough knowledge and awareness regarding cooking practices, childcare practices, and utilization of health services but not adapting them in attitude and practices may be considered one of the reasons for malnutrition. Moreover, if girls belong to larger families (e.g., >7 members) which is quite common, they are more susceptible to undernutrition due to the dilution of household resources. Environmental issues like poor hygiene and sanitation also make the condition worse. Use of pond and canal water for daily purposes and common practices of open defecation due to lack of private toilet facilities increase exposure to pathogens that cause chronic malnutrition. However, primary health care centres and health facilities are accessible in rural areas, but their low utilization with respect to deworming and iron-folic acid (IFA) supplements contributes to infection and illness and other nutrient deficiencies among adolescent girls.

Public health facilities, school-based nutrition education and awareness about malnutrition among mothers and adolescent girls are the proposed solutions to combat the situation. In India, already, many programmes are being run by the government at the ground

level. However, malnutrition is still a major health problem. Many supplementation programmes to improve the nutritional status of young adolescent girls are also in progress. In India, nutrition education intervention programmes through research along with demonstration of low-cost recipes, prepared from easily available local and seasonal foods may be run for rural low socioeconomic status children, adolescent girls, pregnant women and mothers (Jain et al., 2017). Sanitation and hygiene program to reduce recurrent chances of infection and awareness programmes are also conducted through many NGOs and government organizations. Grains, rice and other raw commodities are also provided on subsidized rates to the lower section of society under many government programmes to uplift food and nutrient intake of people (Sreedevi, 2015). However, the target is still far away and our efforts continue to eradicate malnutrition and other micronutrient deficiencies from India.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Addressing malnutrition effectively requires a holistic approach that considers these complex, interrelated factors at the individual, household, and societal levels. Lower socioeconomic status, poor purchasing power, poor educational level, lack of resources, big family structure, poor hygiene and unawareness are various factors associated with it. Apart from these factors, psychosocial and cultural pressure, early marriages add to it. In India, undernutrition among rural adolescent girls is quite high. Global organization like global and national agencies provide funds to run programmes for eradication of undernutrition. These programmes support girls through creating awareness, providing nutrition education, changing their attitude and behaviour for adopting proper cooking practices. Continuous efforts by stakeholders, policy makers and planners are needed to step up and provide cooperation in the betterment of nutritional status of adolescent girls.

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